

Site Suitability Analysis of Water Storage Structures on Kollidam River by using remote sensing and GIS

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Abstract— Concern over how human activity harms the environment and depletes natural resources has grown. This has driven many countries to enact laws ensuring environmental considerations in land use planning. A significant environmental issue is the construction of water storage structures. This has led to a global emphasis on environmental research to find practical solutions for reducing the impacts of such construction. One approach involves using a multi-criteria evaluation technique based on geographic information systems (GIS) to identify optimal water storage locations. This research highlights the use of GIS in mitigating environmental impacts through effective site selection. A case study from Tamil Nadu's Trichy district in Southern India demonstrates this application. The study generated base maps, including the study area boundary, DEM, soil map, and land use data from various sources. The Analytic Hierarchy Process (AHP) was used to determine the importance of each layer. These layers were then overlaid in a GIS to identify suitable sites for water storage. This method enables the selection of potential sites for water storage facilities, demonstrating the successful application of GIS in environmental impact mitigation.

Keywords— GIS, Remote sensing, Thematic mapping, Analytic Hierarchy Process (AHP), Suitable site

I. INTRODUCTION

The imminent availability of water in the foreseeable future for numerous applications especially for dwellings and agricultural irrigation is an enormous worry. Subsequently, it becomes critical for utilizing all of the water in the river basin. This raises serious concerns and limits the application of plans and initiatives for improving the water division. Building storage structures such as check dams, storage tanks, stops dams, and on is one way to tap into water using the water harvesting approach. Water storage acts as a buffer against the unpredictability of rainfall, much like an insurance policy (Payen et al., 2012). In addition to collecting and storing water, water storage facilities can be used to replenish groundwater supplies. They are therefore a crucial part of watershed development (Ahmad and Verma, 2016). Prior to implementation, it is crucial to determine the best site for storage structures because they entail a significant financial commitment. To prevent significant investment it is essential to plan and make decisions about the quantity and kind of water storage structures that must be built using remote sensing and GIS techniques. Thus, it becomes important to identify potential locations for water storage structures. This requires a significant amount of multidisciplinary data from multiple sources, which is made easier by the use of contemporary remote sensing and geographic information system techniques, which allow for the faster and more affordable completion of watershed analyses. The purpose of this article is to use the Multicriteria Evaluation technique to find appropriate locations for water storage in accordance with the Integrated Mission for Sustainable Development principles (IMSD, 1995).

Scope of the Study

Constructing a water storage structures is an important solution for curbing water problems for both domestic and irrigation purpose, Normally kollidam river is a man made water body to handle the abundance water in Cauvery during rainy seasons to avoid flooding of the banks Within the Kollidam River going completely dry for months. For this effort to be achieved successfully, it should be primarily centered on finding a suitable site for dam construction. The main problem is a use of an effective, efficient and accurate method for site selection that will provide accurate terrain investigation and provide adequate information on the selected site for proper planning and design. This will be solved through application of capacities of GIS Technologies in spatial analytical and hydrological modelling.

Study area Description

The study is conducted in the kollidam river estuary. This stream, also known as the Coleroon River, is found within the southeast part of India. The consider region is geologically found at the latitude of $11^{\circ} 4'$ to $10^{\circ} 56'$ N and the longitude of $72^{\circ} 28'$ to $70^{\circ} 40'$ E. The Kollidam River is a northern distributary of Kaveri. Kollidam, which runs to a length of 168 Kms and incorporates a width of 1.8-km branches at Mukkombu to create the Srirangam Island and again at Grand Anicut to travel towards east to enter Bay of Bengal at a place near Kollidam near Sirkazhi in Nagapattiam district. The popular town of Chidambaram is on the banks of Kollidam. Another location explored is a brief 36-kilometer section of the Kollidam River from Mukkombu to Kilikudu (near Kallanai). With the exception of a tiny water flow, this river is often dry all year round (Plate 2). Nevertheless, excess water from the Kaveri at Mukkombu is redirected into this river during the monsoon season. Compared to the Kaveri banks, Kollidam riverbanks are less densely populated. The study area comprises the manachanallur and lalgudi (408.51 sq.km) area of Tiruchirappalli district.

Figure 1: Location map of Kollidam river basin in Tiruchirappalli District

II. MATERIALS AND METHODS

The descriptive methodology is to delineate the dam site suitability location by using spatial data. Using a GIS, the acquired data were scanned and transformed into a digital format to create different layers based on criteria. Using a GIS-based multi-criteria evaluation, the best locations for water storage are determined. This article uses ArcGIS 10.5 to create the thematic maps using satellite data collection. The following criteria have been applied in accordance with the principles of the Integrated Mission for Sustainable Development (IMSD) in order to choose appropriate locations for water storage structures. (IMSD, 1995; Ahmad, I., & Verma, M. K. (2018)):

1. Slopes below 15% are ideal.
2. The land use may be desolate, shrub land and Stream bed.
3. The infiltration rate of the soil ought to be less.
4. The type of soil ought to be sandy clay loam

Figure 2: Methodology for determining the best Site for a Water Storage Structures

III. DATA COLLECTION

By using the different data sources, the base map were created such as DEM, Landuse Land cover, Soil map. Further the base map used to create the thematic map for suitability analysis.

Digital Elevation Model

A model of digital elevation (DEM) is a continuous surface representation typically associated with the earth’s surface. The research area’s data came from USGS Earth Explorer DEM. In order to precise runoff potential, this was done. The graphic displays the kollidam basin’s predicted DEM in Fig 3

Figure 3: Dem of the study area

Landuse/Landcover Map

The relationship between landuse and landcover and the formation of runoff is intricate USGS Earth Explorer was used to create the land use map. A timeline of land usage and cover from May 2020 to April 2024. The Kollidam watershed’s landuse and cover were classified as follows: Water bodies, Savannah, Build up area, Grassland, Cropland, Wasteland. Cropland used for agriculture was determined to be a prominent land use category in the entire watershed. The map of land cover and use displayed in fig 4

Table 1: Landuse pattern of Small Watershed

S.NO	Landuse	Area(ha)	Percentage
1	Savannah	1.8	0.44%
2	Grassland	8.28	2.03%
3	Cropland	391.5	95.84%
4	Built up Area	3.78	0.93%
5	Wasteland	1.8	0.44%
6	Waterbody	1.35	0.33%
	Total	408.51	100.00%

Figure 4: Landuse/Landcover of the study area

Soil map

The properties of the soil surface in this area are intimately related to runoff potential. Runoff is impacted by the presence of gravel and stones. While small stones reduce flow, the presence of huge boulders enhances it. As a result, understanding soil type is crucial. The FAO/UNESCO SOILS PORTAL was used to create the research area's soil map. The soil type present in the study region is sandy clay loam (3.44%) and clay soils (4.58%) can be found in watershed boundary. Fig 5 displays the soil map.

Figure 5: Soil Map of the study area

IV. RESULT AND DISCUSSION

A key factor in choosing a location for a water storage facility is the spatial data on runoff, LULC, slope, soil, stream order, and lineament. The following contains details on these two main levels.

Slope

Slope is a crucial consideration when choosing where to put a storage facility. USGS Earth Explorer is utilized to derive the slope layer, providing a 30 m resolution digital elevation model (DEM) of the slope. The research area has a slope of 0-88.69%. This is then broken down into five smaller groups: Very Gently Sloping (1-3%), Gently Sloping (3-5%), Moderately Sloping (5-10%), and Strongly Sloping (10–15%). Figure 3 (e) displays the slope map of the research region.

Figure 6: Slope Map of the study area

Drainage Order Map

A drainage map of the Kollidam River basin with a drainage range of 0 to 90 was made using DEM and ArcGIS. Stream lines, which show hydrological properties and stream orders from first to fifth, which show the hierarchy and connectivity of streams, were recovered from the DEM by the Spatial Analyst toolkit. The stream order map, shown in Figure 7, visualizes these patterns.

Figure 7: Drainage order Map of the study area

Lineament

In the study area, folds, faults, and fractures are marked as lines. Lineament data is generated using the USGS Earth Explorer DEM and examined in GIS, resulting in the creation of a 100-meter buffer surrounding the lineaments. The lines are displayed in figure 8.

Figure 8: Lineament map of the study area

Runoff Potential

To ascertain the possible runoff in the research area, a curve number (CN) map is created. In essence, CN is a coefficient that lowers rainfall to runoff. It is dependent on two factors: hydrologic soil group (HSG) and land use (Ahmad et al., 2015). The CN is a number between 0 and 100, where 0 denotes no runoff and 100 denotes rainfall equivalent to runoff. The research region has been classed as six landuse land cover area according to NRSC (ISRO), as shown in Figure 4 and Table 2. FAO & UNESCO have provided soil data. ArcGIS is used to transform the same to digital format. Grouping the different types of soil is necessary for the study's objectives. According to USDA Natural Resources Conservation Services (NRCS) (NRCS, 2001; Subramanya, 2013), soil is divided into four groups, known as Hydrologic Soil Group [HSG], A, B, C, and D, based on the ability for infiltration and runoff. Group A soil has an extremely low potential for runoff, Group B has a low potential for runoff, Group C has a moderate potential for runoff, and Group D has a significant potential for runoff. Figure 3 (d) illustrates the regional extent of these soil types.

Table 2: Standard parameters for classifying soil (using the CN approach)

HSG	Soil texture	Runoff potential	Infiltration rate (mm/hr)
A	Sandy, loam sand, sandy loam	low	>7.5
B	Silt or loam	Moderate	3.8-7.5
C	Sandy clay loam	Moderately high	1.3-3.8
D	Clayloam, silty clay loam, silty clay, sandy clay or clay	High	<1.3

Figure 9: Hydrologic soil group of the study area

From the Figure10, the hydrological soil group C and D found in this watershed. It has capability produce moderately high runoff which occupies the area of this small watershed The CN corresponding to HSG were assigned based on NRCS, Which specify the CN for each combination of land use and soil group.

Figure 10: CN Grid of the study area

The CN grid map is obtained through the combination of these two parametric layers. The CN grid map determines the runoff potential; if CN is less than 70, there will be little runoff, moderate runoff between 70 and 85, and high runoff greater than 85.

Figure 11: Runoff Potential Map of the study area

Weighted Overlay Analysis

The Suitability Level Index is used to describe the site suitability of a water storage system. The appropriateness levels for regional dams are ranked from 1 to 9 according to Gosschalk (2002). The study's appropriateness scores fell between one and three. "1" denotes the least suitable, "2" the nearly suitable, and "3" the highly suitable. Table 1 displays the Suitability Level Index that was used in the investigation. Runoff, LULC, slope, type of soil, stream order, and lineament are some of the characteristics that determine suitability level by using spatial data. In order to place the information layers created with their respective weights overlaid on a GIS, the guidelines outlined in Table 3 are put into practice in order to determine the locations of acceptable water storage structures. Each layer is "rasterized" in order to facilitate Weighted Overlay Analysis, as the created layers are in vector format. Following this, all of the raster files are reclassified and the scale value for each unit is provided. There is a scale value from 1 to 3, where 1 represents the least suited, 2 represents the somewhat suitable, and 3 represents the extremely suitable. Table 4 demonstrates how all of the layers are ranked according to how much of an impact they had on the study and how much weight each parameter was assigned. Additionally, the appropriate area has been identified by processing the Weighted Overlay Function in the Spatial Analyst Tool. Using the standards set forth by IMSD, a final map was produced that shows us where water storage sites would be most appropriate to locate. Upon thorough examination of the suitability map, a total of 117 suitable sites were identified. In that are 74 location areas which are highly suitable for constructing a storage structure. 35 locations are moderately suitable and 7 location areas are low suitability in this kollidam river watershed. This representation map was displayed in figure 12.

Table 3: Suitability Level Index for multiple parameters for identifying potential water storage structures

Parameter	SL 1	SL 2	SL 3
Runoff Potential	Low	Moderate	High
LULC	Build Up, Plantation	Forest, Wasteland	Agriculture, Water bodies
Slope	Very steep sloping, Strongly sloping	Gently sloping, Moderately sloping	Nearly level, Very gently sloping
Soil	HSG Group A & B	HSG Group C	HSG Group D
Stream Order	1st & 2nd Order	3rd & 4th Order	5th, 6th & 7thOrder
Lineament	Fracture (100m Buffer)	----	----

Table 3. Weight and Scale Value Allocation for Different Layers

Parameter	Influence(%)	Feature classes	Feature weights
Runoff Potential	15	Moderate High low	2 3 1
LULC	20	Savannah Grassland Cropland Buildup area Wasteland Water bodies	2 2 3 1 3 3
Slope	25	Nearly level Very gently sloping Gently sloping Moderately sloping Strongly sloping	3 3 2 2 1
Soil HSG	10	HSG Group C	2
Stream order	20	1 st order 2 nd order 3 rd order 4 th order 5 th order	1 1 2 2 3
Lineament	10	Fault (100mBuffer)	1

Figure 12: Site suitability map of water storage structure in this Boundary area

V. CONCLUSION

The research investigated emphasizes the significance it is to apply remote sensing and Geographic Information Systems (GIS) to detect suitable locations for water storage facilities in the rapidly urbanizing areas. Massive amounts of spatial and non-spatial data can be managed by utilizing GIS to help determine the most suitable locations for these structures. An authoritative basis for evaluating physical attributes like land use, slope, soil type, stream order, and lineaments is provided by integrating remote sensing with GIS. Sites that optimize water storage capacity while reducing environmental impact are identified by this approach. In the Kollidam River watershed, the study found 116 appropriate locations, of which 74 were extremely suitable, 35 were moderately acceptable, and 7 were lowly suitable

Remedial Measures:

Several crucial corrective actions are advised in order to guarantee the sustainable development of water storage structures:

1. **Erosion Control:** Use retaining walls, vegetation, and silt barriers to stabilize the soil.
2. **Environmental Impact Mitigation:** Use buffer zones to evaluate and lessen ecological impacts.
3. **Community Engagement:** Involve your neighbourhood and offer instruction to promote a sense of ownership.
4. **Structural Integrity:** Plan for climate resilience and conduct routine maintenance.
5. **Water Quality Management:** To avoid contamination, use filtration and keep an eye on the quality of the water.
6. **System Integration:** Link new construction to the water management systems that are already in place.
7. **Adaptive Strategies:** Create strategies to adjust to difficulties and changes in the environment.

By taking these steps, the environmental effects will be reduced and the advantages to the community will be increased, ensuring sustainable water storage options

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